

LAND FORMATION FOR LIVESTOCK CLUSTERS AND THEIR DIFFERENCES

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Abstract. Animal husbandry is one of the most important branches of agriculture, and it is of particular importance among various branches of the national economy. Animal husbandry provides the most necessary food for human life, milk, meat, eggs, honey and fish products. Due to this, land allocation and its rational arrangement for the further expansion of animal husbandry is currently one of the actual issues in agriculture. Therefore, the main purpose of this article is to implement land formation for livestock clusters. According to the results of the research, it is important to rely on the important factors presented in the article when planning land for livestock clusters.

Keywords: agriculture, animal husbandry, land cadastre, land structure, cluster, differences, analysis.

A number of laws, decrees and decisions made by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and our government regarding the development of livestock breeding, which is an integral part of the national economy in the development of our independent republic and the improvement of the well-being of our people, contribute to the development of the sector. In particular, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 8, 2022 No.121 " To increase in livestock and livestock production in livestock complexes organized by cotton-textile, grain and rice clusters in 2022-2024" was adopted [1]. This decision is the most important factor in increasing the production of agricultural products and improving the quality of agricultural products.

The main part of the population of our country, more than 60%, lives in the countryside, and the fact that more than 40% of the population employed in general production is engaged in agriculture indicates how relevant this sector is. For this reason, in the early years of our independence, the President of our Republic issued the Law "On Land", "On Farms", "On Farms" on the development of agriculture, "Law "On Rural Cooperative Farms" were adopted. In particular, in-depth analysis of the results of the work on deepening social, political and economic reforms in our country is bearing fruit [3, 67-70].

The constantly growing industry, housing and other constructions, the establishment of new cities and the expansion of old cities, as well as the need to allocate land for other inhabited places require continuous improvement of land relations based on laws. Management and control of the use of the land fund, improvement of land relations, implementation of the agrarian policy of our country in general is carried out by the State Land Development Service. The constantly growing industry, housing and other constructions, the establishment of new cities and the expansion of old cities, as well as the need to allocate land for other inhabited places require continuous improvement of land relations based on laws.

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Land construction is carried out on the basis of the "Land Code" of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It is considered a system of state measures that ensures the implementation of laws on land use and the decisions of our government, and it is carried out among sectors of the national economy and within sectors. Land preparation works are especially important in the agricultural sector. Creation of new agricultural enterprises, improvement of old ones and organization of their land areas in this area requires the creation of scientifically based projects. Until now, the system of land development works in our country includes the creation and implementation of the General Plan of land use of our republic, regional and district land development plans, inter-farm and intra-farm land development projects, as well as includes other projects related to these works. [4, 23-25]. These projects include measures aimed at stopping soil erosion and ending its consequences, improving land reclamation, pollution and agricultural abandonment.

As a result of the development of science and technology, new techniques, technologies, methods of agrotechnics and labor organization, new types and varieties of crops, new types and breeds of agricultural animals enter the field of agriculture. This, in turn, in order to efficiently use the land and other means of production, the means of production inseparably connected with the land (ditches, roads, houses, warehouses, sheds, water structures, etc.) requires deployment. Thus, land formation is a system of activities aimed at implementing the land laws of the state, which is aimed at the full, rational and effective use of the land and the means of production and labor resources that are inextricably linked with the land. [2, 79-85].

The composition of land preparation works for livestock clusters is mainly based on the requirements of production organization in the sectors of the national economy. Currently, land preparation works for livestock clusters include the following main tasks:

- carrying out necessary research for topography, geodesy, cartography, geobotany, soil and other land formation;
- working out the Master plan of land use and its protection in our republic, the plans of land formation of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and districts;
- creation of land protection and land use projects;
- organization of new farms in livestock clusters and elimination of deficiencies in the location of land areas of existing farms, drawing up projects for allocating land areas to farms;
- working on internal land development projects in livestock farms (including leased and private farms);
- identification of land areas of great importance for nature protection and organization of works aimed at nature protection on the land, as well as organization of recreation centers and nature reserves in beautiful places of nature, etc.

The tasks of organizing areas of pastures and hayfields for livestock clusters:
increase their productivity;

improving the botanical composition of plants;

reasonable use is to create a solid feed base for livestock.

Before working on the project of organizing the areas of pastures and hayfields for livestock clusters, their current condition and use will be studied. It is held to determine the next order

of use of each plot, to work on measures to improve pastures, hayfields, and to draw up land areas. The study of some pasture and hayfield plots is carried out according to the following: relief (location, slope direction and slope); soils (types, mechanical composition, moisture content, salinity, humus content); plants (type of grasses, their nutritional value, pastures, productivity of hayfields, green mass output by months of the pasture period): cultural and technical condition (grains, bushes, forest trees, stones, etc.); from livestock farms, summer camps, water sources. distance from residential areas; the depth of the groundwater level and the conditions of water supply, the supply of water sources. It is necessary to study the existing organization of pastures and hayfields (attachment of pastures to farms, herds, groups of cattle, pasture exchanges, availability of hayfield exchange plots, their location, location of water sources, water reserves or outflow).

The main attention should be paid to the natural condition of plots intended for irrigated cultural pastures and hayfields, as well as their suitability for creating a layer of high-yielding pastures and hayfield grasses, and their rational use, in terms of irrigation conditions. In the study of fertile soil, researches of working projects on soil structure, geobotany, water management, pasture and hayfield improvement are used.

The organization of the territory of pastures for livestock clusters will consist of the following: from attaching pastures to livestock farms, complexes from organizing pasture exchanges; from the placement of herds and herd plots, summer camps, water sources and watering places, roads for driving cattle.

Conclusion. Animal husbandry clusters mean the simultaneous development of all branches of animal husbandry, i.e. poultry, cattle breeding, sheep breeding and similar branches. Allocation of land plots for the development of livestock clusters is of great importance in this area. Due to this, it is an important issue to implement the tasks presented in the implementation of land planning for livestock clusters.

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